

SOME FEATURES OF TEACHING SPEAKING IN ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Badalova Luiza Kholmamatovna

Karshi engineering - economics Institute,
Senior teacher at Foreign Languages Department

Abstract: Speaking is one of the most important goals that all students and teachers strive for, it is one of the main reasons why students start learning a foreign language. The desire to perceive and convey information, interact with native speakers of the language being studied is exactly what foreign language teaching is focused on today. The article discusses the features of teaching speaking in a foreign language, shows the specifics of speaking as a type of speech activity, outlines the structure of the process of speech production, characterizes the dialogic and monologue types of speaking.

Keywords: communicative competence, teaching speaking, teaching techniques, speech interaction

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INTRODUCTION:

In the context of reforming higher education, issues related to the implementation of new goals for teaching English, the main of which is the creation of a speech base for further systematic teaching of English on a communicative basis, have become particularly relevant. The acquisition of communicative competence by students involves the development of their oral and written speech. The oral form of speech, as we know, is primary, so it is necessary to take care of the correct construction of various types and types of statements in oral form.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

The problem of the formation and development of oral speech (speaking) in the scientific literature is not new, but methodological advice and recommendations for teaching schoolchildren to speak in linguodidactics are not enough. This question attracts the attention of M. Bazina, Alieva Yu.A., I. Zimnaya, E. Passov, V. Artemov, E. Solovova and other scientists. Speaking is divided into dialogic and monologue statements. Speaking is the expression of one's thoughts in order to solve the problems of communication. This is the activity of one person, although it is included in communication and is unthinkable outside of it, because communication is always interaction with other people. The goal of schooling should be considered not language, which is appropriate for philological education in a special university, and not speech, as "a way of forming and formulating thoughts" (N.A. Zimnyaya), and not even just speech activity - speaking, reading, listening or a letter, but the indicated types of speech activity as a means of

communication. In relation to speaking, this means that it, together with paralinguistic (facial expressions, gestures) and proxemics (movement, postures), serves as a means of implementing an oral form of communication. Such a goal requires an appropriate method to achieve it. For speaking, it is a communicative method. The foregoing determines the most important starting point: it is impossible to teach speaking without teaching communication, without creating conditions for verbal communication in the classroom. The subject of communication is the relationship of the interlocutors.

It is in the subject that the need is realized, as a result of which it becomes the motive of activity. This means that the motive for communication cannot arise if there is no relationship (subject) or they are not recognized. The purpose of communication is to solve problems related to relationships, that is, to change them. The means by which the goal of oral communication is achieved are speaking, listening and paralinguistics.

The product of communication is the interpretation of information. There are three ways of communication: perceptual, interactive and informational, as well as two types of communication: role-playing and personal. These are the main characteristics of communication (Artemov V.A.).

DISCUSSIONS:

Let us now look from this point of view at what the process of teaching foreign language speaking should be like.

1) Between the teacher and the student, any relationship must be established, except for official ones, i.e. communication should not be role-based (teacher-student), but communication of individuals who see each other as a speech partner.

2) The motive for communication can appear only when there is a need for genuine communication. The need for "learning" communication, which some students have, is different in nature and is not able to provide communicative motivation.

3) If the relationship between the teacher and students as between individuals does not arise, then there is no goal inherent in communication to change these relationships.

4) All methods of communication must function: interactive, when there is interaction based on any activity other than educational; perceptual, when there is a perception of each other as individuals; informational, when students exchange their thoughts, feelings. If the student retells the text only for the sake of retelling (when everyone in the class knows its content) or pronounces some non-situational sentences, then communication cannot take place, and the product of such speaking is the so-called educational speech. It is necessary to give the learning process,

without violating its organization, systemic and methodological orientation, and the characteristic features of the communication process.

Speaking is a type of speech activity through which oral verbal communication is carried out. It can have varying complexity, ranging from expressing an effective state with a simple exclamation, naming an object, answering a question, and ending with an independent detailed statement. The transition from a word and a phrase to a whole statement is associated with varying degrees of participation of thinking and memory. The term oral language training is used quite often. Therefore, we will use the term "learning to speak", meaning by it learning to express one's thoughts orally [29, 1415].

The learning objective should be defined as speaking at skill level. For the implementation of speaking, certain conditions are necessary. In connection with the presence of these conditions, it is interesting to pay attention to the following fact. In the process of learning to speak, there is a "conflict" between meaningful and logical speech, on the one hand, and its productivity, on the other. The presence of knowledge, thoughts, and desire to express one's attitude to something comes up against the lack of means of expression. Apparently, with the traditional organization of speech material (with a non-communicative approach to teaching speaking), this "conflict" (between "I want" and "I can") is unresolvable. Assimilation of tenses, for example, is separated by a significant interval, which makes it impossible to express thoughts naturally and leads, among other things, to a loss of interest in a foreign language as a means of communication.

Almost all modern methods insist on the communicative orientation of training. Today it is especially popular. The greatest difficulties in foreign language communication a person experiences, perceiving speech by ear. However, oral communication, the role of which has now become especially significant, is impossible without understanding the speech of the interlocutor, since in the process of speech interaction everyone acts both as a speaker and as a listener. One of the most controversial aspects of the problem of teaching foreign languages is the verification and accounting of knowledge, skills and abilities, the methodology for their organization and implementation[31,112].

What does learning to speak involve?

- Mastery of communication skills involves:
- Reproduction of sounds and sound models;
- The use of intonation patterns and rhythms, the correct placement of stress in words and sentences;
- Selection of suitable words and types of sentences depending on the audience, social setting, topic and situation;

- Organization of thoughts in a logical sequence; the use of English as a means of expressing judgments;

- Ability to speak English fluently and with few pauses.

Dialogue and monologue forms of communication in teaching.

When teaching speaking in English, two forms of communication are distinguished: dialogical and monologue. Both forms are important, but still, special attention is paid to the dialogic form, since it is more communicatively directed.

The dialogic form of communication is the most characteristic of the communicative function of language. Its development involves not only the ability to compose the correct answer to the question of the interlocutor or correctly ask the question. This is important, but in addition to this, you need to be able to express agreement / disagreement, express regret, apology, delight and joy, displeasure, etc. Knowledge of the topic material (vocabulary, speech patterns, grammar information) and the ability to work with visual aids are also required, skills and abilities to correctly select and use appropriate speech samples (typical phrases) with the required lexical content [24, 14].

As for the monologic form of communication, the units of teaching a monologic utterance are sentences, superphrasal units and a coherent text. At the first level (reproductive) speech creativity of students is not expected, therefore, the language design and content are determined by the teacher. The second level (reproductive-productive) involves some elements of independence and creativity in statements. The third level is the level of productive monologue speech. At this stage, the student can, on the basis of his own language and speech experience, express his attitude to events and facts, give an assessment, build his statement according to his own plan. Scientists and linguists have identified the main types of speech activity that stimulate speaking. The main ones are listed below:

Discussion- A discussion during training can be organized in many ways, it can be aimed at exchanging views on an event, expressing thoughts about the material read and listened to, jointly searching for a solution to a particular problem, etc. For discussion, groups of 3– 5 people, they are provided with controversial topics for discussion. It is important that each member of the group has the opportunity to speak. This type of activity contributes to rapid decision-making and the development of critical thinking.

Role-playing games- In this type of activity, participants must represent themselves in different social contexts and play different social roles. In such games, the teacher for learning must provide the participants with certain information: who they are, what they feel and what they think about this or that occasion.

Simulation models- Simulation models are essentially the same as role-playing games, only in a more complex and thoughtful form. To give realism to a particular situation, various objects and auxiliary materials are used during training. Information gaps. This activity is designed to work in pairs. Pupils have this or that information, which they exchange among themselves. In the process of information exchange, any problems should be solved or information should be collected. Each of the participants in the dialogue is equally important, therefore only two participants will be able to recreate the information provided to them as accurately and fully as possible.

Brainstorm- This type of activity involves learning to produce ideas on a given topic in a strictly limited period. Brainstorming can be used both for groups of participants, and for each taken separately.

Interview -English learners conduct interviews on selected topics with various people. They draw up a plan and questions for the interview on their own; the teacher can only indicate the topic.

The end of the story- Quite an interesting and productive activity. The teacher tells the story, but not to the end, stopping before the denouement. Then each of the participants offers their own ending.

Description by pictures- The teacher offers a picture or a series of pictures, and the students must describe what is shown in the picture, or make up a story from a series of pictures.

Report- Each student must prepare a story on a given topic before class, and then, in a concise form, following the logic of the narrative, present the processed information.

Speaking is closely related to other types of speech activity: listening, reading and writing. The connection between speaking and listening is due to complex mental activity based on inner speech and the prediction mechanism.

CONCLUSION:

Thus, at present, teaching foreign languages, in particular speaking, is considered as teaching communicative activity, the ability to communicate. In this regard, the search for innovative forms and methods of teaching should be carried out to develop professionally oriented student learning, improve the quality of foreign language classes, and increase their effectiveness.

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